

Studies on 3d-Metal Complexes of Acetylacetonethioxythiocarbonyl Hydrazone

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3d metal complexes $M(\text{acac eth})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$M = \text{Mn(II)}, \text{Fe(II)}, \text{Co(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}, \text{Cu(II)}$ or Zn(II)] of acetylacetonethioxythiocarbonyl hydrazone ($\text{H}_2\text{acac eth}$) and $[\text{Ni(eth)}_2\text{acacH}]$ have been prepared. Magnetic moment and electronic spectra suggest tetrahedral geometry for Co(II) , square-planar geometry for Ni(II) and Cu(II) and octahedral geometry for Fe(II) complex. ESR spectra of $\text{Cu(acac eth)}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggest that the unpaired electron is present in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu(II) . Infrared spectral studies show dinegative tridentate behaviour of the ligand in $M(\text{acac eth})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

A few reports are available on the transition metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from the condensation of acetylacetonethiosemicarbazide¹ and S-methyl dithiocarbamate². The present communication describes the results of our investigations on the title complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H. or equivalent quality. Acetylacetonethioxythiocarbonyl hydra-

zone, $\text{CH}_3 - \overset{\text{O}}{\parallel} \text{C} - \text{CH}_2 - \overset{\text{CH}_3}{\underset{|}{\text{C}}} = \text{N} - \text{NH} - \overset{\text{S}}{\parallel} \text{C} - \text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$ ($\text{H}_2\text{acac eth}$) was prepared by refluxing for ~1 hr ethanolic solutions of freshly distilled acetylacetonethioxythiocarbonyl hydrazide in ~1.5 : 1 molar ratio, cooling and then adding excess of water. The oily layer thus formed was separated out and washed with small portions of distilled water, 2% HCl and finally with water. The resulting oily product was dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl_2 , yield ~40%, b.p. 122-124/4 mm. (Found : C, 47.20; H, 7.02; N, 13.68; S, 16.02; N_2H_4 , 15.65. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 47.52; H, 6.93; N, 13.86; S, 15.85; N_2H_4 , 15.85%). Ethoxythiocarbonyl hydrazide required for the purpose was prepared by the method of Jenson *et al*³.

Preparation and analysis of the complexes : The complexes $M(\text{acac eth})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$M = \text{Mn(II)}, \text{Co(II)}, \text{Ni(II)}, \text{Cu(II)}$ or Zn(II)] were prepared by mixing together aqueous solution of the metal(II) acetate and ethanolic solution of $[\text{H}_2\text{acac eth}]$ in ~1 : 1 molar ratio followed by the addition of aq. sodium acetate in all cases except in the case of Mn(II) complex, where a few drops of dil. NH_4OH were added.

$\text{Fe(acac eth)}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{acac eth}]$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio and then adding ethanolic KOH drop by drop to the reaction mixture in hydrogen atmosphere.

The complexes thus precipitated were digested on water bath for 10 min, cooled, suction filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. $[\text{Ni(eth)}_2\text{acacH}]$ was prepared by refluxing a suspension of bis(ethoxythiocarbonyl hydrazidato)Ni(II) in ethanol with excess of acetylacetonethioxythiocarbonyl hydrazide (~1 : 5 molar ratio) for ~4 hr or till the yellow colour of the starting complex completely changed to bright red. The product was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Bis(ethoxythiocarbonyl hydrazidato)Ni(II) required for the purpose was prepared by reacting $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ethoxythiocarbonyl hydrazide hydrochloride³ in ethanol in ~1 : 2 molar ratio and raising the pH to ~5-6 with dil. NH_4OH . The complexes were analysed for their metal contents employing standard procedures after destroying the organic matter first with a mixture of nitric and hydrochloric acids and then with sulphuric acid. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 . Nitrogen was determined by microanalysis. Hydrazine was estimated volumetrically using KIO_3 after refluxing the complexes in ~7N HCl for 2 to 3 hr. The water content was determined by heating the complexes in the temperature range 120-140° and determining the loss in weight. The analytical data are given in Table I.

Physical measurements :

The equipments and the methods employed for recording magnetic susceptibility, esr, electronic and infrared spectra were the same as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data given in Table I show the formation of complexes of the type $M(\text{acac eth})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the loss of two protons from the ligand. The loss in weight on heating the complexes at 120-140° corresponds to the presence of one water molecule and indicates its coordinated nature⁵. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents like the other known complexes of ONS donor ligands⁷. $[\text{Ni(eth)}_2\text{acacH}]$ dissolves in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF $[H_2acac\ eth]$ COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis% : Found/(Caled.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		Metal	N	N_2H_4	S	
Mn(acac eth).H ₂ O	Light yellow	20.02 (20.18)	10.18 (10.25)	11.90 (11.72)	11.58 (11.72)	5.46
Fe(acac eth).H ₂ O	Brown	20.12 (20.39)	10.20 (10.23)	— (11.68)	11.50 (11.68)	4.81
Co(acac eth).H ₂ O	Green	21.14 (21.28)	10.02 (10.12)	11.49 (11.57)	11.68 (11.57)	4.20
Ni(acac eth).H ₂ O	Brown	21.06 (21.22)	11.78 (11.97)	11.62 (11.58)	11.78 (11.58)	Diamagnetic
Cu(acac eth).H ₂ O	Violet	22.38 (22.59)	10.88 (10.91)	11.44 (11.37)	11.08 (11.37)	1.91
Zn(acac eth).H ₂ O	White	23.21 (23.07)	10.10 (9.91)	11.58 (11.29)	11.41 (11.29)	Diamagnetic
[Ni(eth) ₂ acacH]	Red	16.20 (16.28)	15.72 (15.53)	17.58 (17.75)	17.60 (17.75)	Diamagnetic

alcoholic KOH showing the acid character of the methylene proton of the acetylacetonone part of the ligand.

Magnetic moments :

The magnetic moment data given in Table 1 show that Mn(II) and Fe(II) form spin-free complexes. The diamagnetism of Ni(II) complexes and μ_{eff} value of 4.2 for Co(II) complex suggest that the former complexes are square planar and the later is tetrahedral. The magnetic moment of Cu(II) complex corresponds well with the presence of one unpaired electron and gives no specific information about its stereochemistry.

Electronic spectra :

The uv spectrum of the ligand in ethanol shows two bands at 35710 and 43480 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the $>C=S$ and $>C=O$ chromophores, respectively present in the ligand⁸.

The spectrum of Fe(acac eth).H₂O shows one broad band at 11430 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^6T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g(D)$ transition in octahedral geometry of the complex⁹.

The spectrum of Co(acac eth).H₂O shows three d—d transitions at 9800, 16530 and 17390 cm^{-1} characteristic of tetrahedral geometry around Co(II)⁹. The first band may therefore be attributed to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ (ν_2) and the second and third to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ (ν_3) transitions. The values of 10 Dq and B, calculated by the method of Lever¹⁰ after taking ν_3 as the average¹¹ of the two split bands come to 3700 and 617 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The spectrum of Ni(acac eth).H₂O yields two d—d transitions at 15150 and 21100 cm^{-1} which are shifted to slightly higher energies viz., 16000 and 22000 cm^{-1} , respectively in the spectrum of the anhydrous compound. The above bands in each case may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively in square planar geometry of the complex⁹. The occurrence of the d—d bands at higher energies in the anhydrous compound may be due to an increase in the ligand field strength

around Ni(II) in going from hydrated to the anhydrous complex.

The spectrum of $[Ni(eth)_2acacH]$ shows two d—d bands at 20830 and 24100 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively in square planar geometry of the complex. The colour of the complex and the position of the first d—d transition band suggest *cis*-square planar geometry for the complex¹² (Fig. 1c). The single electron parameters Δ_1 and Δ_2 have been calculated for Ni(acac eth).H₂O, Ni(acac eth) and $[Ni(eth)_2acacH]$ and come out to be 17950, 7500; 18800, 7600; and 23630, 4870 cm^{-1} , respectively^{13, 14}. The occurrence of d—d transition band at 20000 cm^{-1} in Cu(acac eth).H₂O suggests its square planar geometry which may be assigned to the envelop of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$ and 2E_g transitions¹⁵.

ESR spectra :

Cu(acac eth).H₂O shows isotropic esr spectrum at room temperature and nearly axially symmetric at 77 K. The values of the various esr magnetic parameters calculated from the spectra are as given below :

$g_{av} = 2.069$; $g_{||} = 2.177$; $g_{\perp} = 2.041$; $A_{iso}(Cu) = 93.3$ G; $A_{||}(Cu) = 180$ G and $A_{\perp} = 50$ G.

The trend $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > g_0$ (free spin value, 2.0023) observed for the complex indicates that the unpaired electron is most likely in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu(II). This is further supported by the $(g_{||} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$ ratio which equals 4.3¹⁵.

NMR spectra :

The 1H nmr spectrum of acetylacetonone ethoxythiocarbonyl hydrazone ($H_2acac\ eth$) recorded on a varian A-60 D spectrophotometer in CCl_4 shows signals at δ 1.40 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 3H, $-OCH_2CH_3$),

1.93 [s, $CH_3 - C(=O) - O$], 2.08 (s, $CH_3 - C=N-$),

δ_A 2.82, δ_B 3.17 (q, $J_{AB} = 18$ Hz, 2H, $-CH_2-$), 4.58 (q, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H, $-OCH_2 - CH_3$) and 8.20–8.75 (br, s, $-NH-$). Additional weak intensity CH_3

proton signals at δ 2.00 and 2.25 may be due to the presence of enolic tautomer of the ligand. ^1H NMR spectral studies thus suggest co-existence of keto-enol form of the ligand in solution. The insolubility of the complexes in common solvents precluded their ^1H nmr spectral studies.

IR spectra :

The infrared spectrum (neat) of $(\text{H}_3\text{acac eth})$ shows a strong intensity band at $3260\text{-}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which disappears in the complexes due to the removal of NH and OH protons while a new broad band of weak to medium intensity is observed in $3350\text{-}3480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, probably due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the water molecule. A strong band at 1740 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is found to be absent in the spectra of the complexes suggesting the disappearance of the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group via enolisation and subsequent removal of the enolic proton. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band occurring at 1635 cm^{-1} in the ligand suffers a negative shift of 10 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Ni}(\text{eth})_2\text{acacH}]$, indicating that the nitrogen of this group is coordinated to nickel(II). This band, however, disappears in other complexes and new bands appear in $1495\text{-}1550$ and $1510\text{-}1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ modes, respectively¹⁶. A positive shift of $10\text{-}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ shows that only one of the nitrogen of N-N moiety is involved in bonding¹⁷.

Bands appearing at 1430 and 870 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand are assigned to thioamide I and IV bands, respectively. The disappearance of thioamide IV band and a positive shift of $60\text{-}85\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in thioamide I band and appearance of a new band in $710\text{-}730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in the spectra of the complexes suggest bonding through 'thiolo' sulphur¹⁶⁻²⁰.

The non-ligand bands occurring in $420\text{-}450$, $300\text{-}335$ and $360\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions may be tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ modes, respectively^{20,21}.

On the basis of analytical data and physico-chemical studies discussed above, structures shown in Figs. 1a, 1b and 1c may be proposed for the complexes.

$\text{M}(\text{acac eth})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{M}=\text{Ni}(\text{II}), \text{Cu}(\text{II})$

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

$[\text{Ni}(\text{eth})_2\text{acacH}]$

Fig. 1c

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